

Role of Selected Stakeholders in the Administration of Selected Private Primary Schools in Bo City

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Abstract— This study was carried out in Bo city, Southern Province, Republic of Sierra Leone. Bo city is the third largest city in Sierra Leone by population (after Freetown and Kenema) and the largest city in the Southern Province. Bo is the capital and administrative center of Bo District. The city of Bo had a population of 149,957 in the 2004 census and has an estimated current population of about 175,000. [8][9][3][5][10] Bo is an urban center, and lies approximately 160 miles (250 km) east south-east of Freetown, and about 44 miles to Kenema. [11] Bo is the leading financial, educational and economic center of Southern Sierra Leone. Bo was previously the second largest city in Sierra Leone by population, However, Kenema over took Bo in population after the 2015 Sierra Leone national census.

This study is initiated to find out the roles of stakeholders like the ministry of Basic Education, proprietors, members of the School Management Committee (S.M.C), and members of the community Teachers Association (C.T.A), Headmasters (H.M) and senior Teachers (S.T) in the administration of private primary schools in Bo City. The research hypothesized that those components like proprietors, Head teachers, the school Management Committee, members of the Community Teachers Association, Supervisor of the Ministry of Education and Senior Teachers are among the key players in maintaining and running private primary schools.

The results of this study have proven that several individuals and groups have significant roles to play in the administration of private primary schools. Such individuals and groups include proprietors, Head teachers, the School Management Committees, CTA and officials of the Ministry of the Education. Without cooperation among these major players in the administration of private primary schools, it will be difficult if not impossible for private schools to function well. Getting a good private primary school depends on apportioning tasks to these key stakeholders in the administration of private primary schools and making sure that such tasks are performed in the most efficient manner.

This study also revealed that proprietors of private primary schools more or less act like entrepreneurs in any business establishment. They provide one of the basic components of administrative funds. With funds, others deliver the service of teaching to the client (pupils).

Another key stakeholder in the administration of private primary schools is the Head teacher. He plays the role of an administrator and supervisor, because apart from defining and apportioning tasks to teachers, he/she sees to it that such tasks are carried out appropriately. The Head teacher also acts as a bridge between the school and the proprietor, the school and the School Management, the schools and the Ministry of Education.

Under the Ministry of Education, the inspectorate helps the government to run all educational policies smoothly. Their frequent visit to private primary schools is to make sure that the educational policy set up by government is implemented to the letter.

The Schools Management Committee more or less acts as an advisory council and the brain behind what operates in private

primary schools. They brainstorm and suggest positive ways that may bring development and raise the standard of the school.

Whereas proprietors provide the initial funds raised for the establishment of a private primary school, parents by paying the children's school fees help to recycle the school's finances which keep the school functioning. The parents lighten the burden on the school administrators by complementing the efforts of the schools. They study or make arrangements for the studying of their children, they encourage and motivate both their children and teachers when they give complements or show appreciation for good work done.

This study has further proven that, the roles and responsibilities of major stakeholders in the administration of private primary schools is not uniform for all private primary schools. What is the responsibility of the proprietor in one school for instance might be the responsibility of a Head teacher in another school. However, there are many areas where uniformity has been discovered and reported.

I. INTRODUCTION

We see innocent Children go to school daily and after some years they develop into responsible adults serviceable to themselves and their society. The school did not evolve accidentally, but it is the conscious effort of certain people (administrators) to socialize young ones and make them fit to live in society. Hence, Society has the responsibility of socializing its members to ensure its continuity. Among the primary agents of socialization is the school. The school as one of the most important institutions in society is entrusted with the Herculean task of developing the child into a viable citizen useful to himself and serviceable to his society.

For the school to realize its aim, there must be set programs specifically designed by policy makers and curriculum planners and people assigned with the responsibility of implementing such programs. It is education administrators that transform policies into actions. Educational policies which are normally designed by governments, missions, individuals, or group of individuals will be result oriented only when there are staff / personnel to implement such policies in the school.

According to O.C. Abose, and J.B.A. Amissah (1992) Administration is "A process of getting things done through the effort of other people". Every administration has some form of organization. The type of administration would depend on the service the group intends to deliver. The school administration renders the service of learning like the police for instance provides security to name but a few. The term educational Administration is very elastic and therefore difficult to define; the focus here should be "Educational" which is a qualifier. In defining Educational Administration

there are two concepts we have to take into account: Management and Administration. Management involves planning, designing, initiating actions monitoring activities, and demanding result on the basis of allocated resources. Administration on the other hand involves coordinating, controlling, and evaluating. Some people use the terms Management and Administration interchangeably. According to Ron gather (1972) “We see no difference in practice between Management and Administration”.

Educational Administration is the process of coordinating the efforts of the people towards achievement of a desired goal i.e. Teaching and learning. Page and Thomas (1978).

In many countries of the world, the responsibility of educating the people lies on the state. That is, it is the state through the ministry of Education that generates Educational Acts, policies, gives directives to academic staff/ personnel and also pays school administrators and their staffs.

Some countries have Education Acts that make provision for decentralization of education. In this system, autonomy is given to regions or state within a country to formulate policies, give directives and pay administrators and their staffs. Nigeria is an example as it has a decentralized educational system. Other countries like Sierra Leone maintain a centralized educational pattern, where Education Acts, Policies and payment of administrators and teachers are the sole responsibility of the central Government through the ministry of Education.

It is important to note also that many countries through Acts of Parliament have liberalized education because of one reason or the other. Sometimes because states are poor and cannot bear the sole responsibility of educating the citizens, they may liberalize education. As a result of this process, there has been a rapid upsurge of private schools, colleges and universities in different countries in the world to complete or complement the effort of government in managing education.

Today, many people in Sierra Leone. The privileged and even the under privileged prefer sending their children to private schools possibly for better care and learning even with the free and quality education in the country. An educationist may be concerned about the rapid progress private institutions and schools are making. He starts to ponder and tries to unravel certain riddles. He may ask himself questions like: Is it the administrative pattern of private schools that account for success? Such questions are always asked by educationists but the answers are never the same.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To carry out this study, questionnaires were explicitly prepared for head teachers, proprietors, and members of the Schools Management Committee, members of the Community Teachers Association, Senior Teachers and Inspectors / Supervisors of private primary schools. Questionnaires were to elicit information as to what role each of these components plays in the research guesses about what these people or group of people do to administer private Primary Schools. Apart from issuing out questionnaires, formal and informal interviews were conducted with the key players in the administration of private schools. Data collected from the

study were analyzed using tables: Such tables displayed quantitative information about what proprietors, Head teachers, members of CTA, SMC and Inspectors of schools do to keep private schools functioning. The study was based on five randomly selected private Primary Schools in Bo City. The findings obtained from the investigation have been exhausted and discussed using the objectives of the study.

Objectives of the study

This study focused on investigating and identifying roles of major stakeholders in the administration of private primary schools in Bo City with the following specific objectives:

1. To investigate the functions/roles played by key stakeholders in the Administration of private primary schools.
2. To identify the constraints of the participants in the administration of private primary schools.
3. To solicit suggestions from participants in their roles in the administration of private primary schools in Bo city.
4. To make appropriate recommendations/suggestions to enhance the administration of private primary schools in the Bo City.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

TABLE 1: Number and percentage of distribution of respondents (stakeholders) interviewed in the study.

Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Managers	5	5%
Education secretaries	5	5%
Deputy Director of Education	1	1%
Inspector of Schools	2	2%
Supervisor of Schools	7	7%
School Management Committee (SMC)	20	20%
Community Teachers Association (CTA)	50	50%
Head Teachers	5	5%
Deputy Head Teachers	5	5%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table one reveals that among the respondents interviewed, 50% were members of the community teachers association (CTA), 20 members of the school management committee (SMC) 7% Supervisor of Private Primary Schools, 2% Inspector of Private Schools, 1% deputy director of education, while 5% were managers, education secretaries, head teachers and deputy head teachers.

TABLE 2: number of percentage distribution of respondents and their qualifications (proprietors, ministry officers, school heads, SMC and CTA Members)

Qualification	Proprietors		MEYS Officials		SMC		CTA		School Heads	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
T.C	0	-	1	10%	4	20%	2	4%	1	10%
H.T.C	2	20%	4	40%	6	30%	6	12%	3	30%
1 ST Degree	5	50%	3	30%	7	35%	2	4%	4	40%
2 nd Degree	1	10%	2	20%	-	-	1	2%	2	20%
Others	2	20%	-	-	3	15%	3	6%	-	-
None	-	-	-	-	-	-	36	72%	-	-
Total	10	100%	10	100%	20	100	50	100	10	100

Table 2 indicates that 50% of the proprietors had Bachelor Degree, 10% post graduates in Education, 20% Higher Teachers Certificate (HTC) and others such as Ordinary Diplomas (OND) and Higher National Diploma (HND). Among the Officials of the Ministry of Education, 10% had Teachers Certificate (TC), 40% H.T.C, 30% Bachelor Degree and 20% Masters' Degree in Education.

Similarly 20% SMC members had T.C, 30% H.T.C, 35% First Degree and 15% other qualifications like Diplomas (OND and HND). 72% of members of the Community Teachers Association (CTA) were non literate, 4% had T.C, 12% HTC, 4% Bachelor of Degree, 2% Masters' Degrees and 6% others such as OND and HND.

Likewise 10% of the school heads had TC, 30% HTC, 40% Bachelor Degrees and 20% Masters' Degree in Education.

TABLE 3: Number and percentage Distribution of Respondent's Job experience in years (Ministry Officers, Proprietors and School Heads)

Experience in Years	Proprietors		Ministry of Education Officials		School Heads	
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage	No	Percentage
1-9 years	4	40%	3	30%	2	20%
10-19 years	5	50%	7	70%	5	50%
20 yrs. and above	1	10%	-	-	3	30%
Total	10	100%	10	100%	10	100%

From the above, it could be deduced that 40% of the proprietors had working experience ranging from 1-9 years, 50% between 10-years and 10% above 20 years. Similarly 30% of the workers in the Ministry of Education had experience between 1-9 years, 70% between 10-19 years and non above 20 years. This points out that a high percentage of the interviewees had an adequate knowledge of the job they are dispensing.

TABLE 4: Number and Percentage Distribution of Administrative Roles played by Respondents in their various Schools (Proprietors, School Heads and Deputies)

Roles/responsibilities	Proprietors		Head Teaches		Deputy Head Teachers	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Establishing rules and Regulations of the School	10	100%	1	20%	1	20%
Appointment of Head of Schools and Teachers	10	100%	-	-	-	-
Prepares job description for teachers and other staff	10	100%	2	40%	3	60%
Maintaining discipline in the School	10	100%	2	40%	1	20%
Monitoring and Evaluating School Activities and Programs	10	100%	-	-	-	-
Determines conditions of service for teachers and other workers	10	100%	-	-	-	-
Total	0	100%	1	100%	10	100%

The information from table 4 reveals that all (100%) proprietors indicated playing the following roles in the administration of their schools:- Establishing School Rules and Regulations, Appointment of School Heads and Teachers, Preparation of Job Description, Maintaining Discipline in Schools, Monitoring and Evaluating of School Activities and Programmes, and Designing Conditions of Services for Teachers and other Workers.

Among the head teachers, 20% mentioned establishing rules and regulations for their schools, 40% cited designing job description for teachers and other workers and maintaining discipline in schools respectively.

In addendum, among the deputy head teachers, 20% mentioned establishing school rules and regulations, 60% designs job description for teachers and other staff and 20% mentioned maintaining discipline in schools.

TABLE 5: Number and percentage distribution of respondents (ministry officials) roles/duties to private primary schools in Bo City.

ROLES/DUTIES	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Recommend and estimate cost of teaching/learning materials	10	100%
Inspect school records, lesson notes of teachers and pupils performance	10	100%
Inspect school facilities and recommend areas for improvement	10	100%
Organize workshops and professional leadership among school heads and teachers	10	100%
Advise on teacher recruitment as well as promotions for deserving teachers	10	100%
Report and recommend findings to proprietors and central government for necessary actions	10	100%
TOTAL	110	100%

Table 5: gives highlights of some of the roles/responsibilities performed by officials in the Ministry of Education in private primary schools in the Bo City.

Among the many functions, the most important areas are indicated in the table. As indicated, all (100%) Ministry Officials expressed the following:

Recommendation and estimating cost of teaching/learning materials especially on cost recovery basis

Inspecting school records and teaching notes of teachers as well as pupils performance

Supervising school facilities and recommending areas of improvement.

Organize workshops and provide professional leadership among school heads and teachers.

Report and recommend findings to proprietors and central government for necessary action that may facilitate development in educational sector.

TABLE 6: Number and percentage distribution of respondents (ministry officials) number of visits to private primary schools

NUMBER OF VISITS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Once per term	3	30%
Twice per term	5	50%
Thrice per term	2	20%
Once a year	-	-
TOTAL	10	100%

As projected in table 6, 30% of the ministry officials visit private primary schools once per term. 50% indicated twice per term and 20% three times per term. None indicated once a year. Considering the number of private primary schools in the Bo City and the number of officials in the branch ministry, it could be deduced that such visits are not adequate for proper supervision, monitoring and evaluation purposes.

TABLE 7: number and percentage distribution of constraints experienced by respondents (ministry officials) in their work with private primary schools

CONSTRAINTS/RECOMMENDATIONS	NUMBER	PERCEIVED
Understaffing especially in specialized areas	10	100%
Not enough time to discuss with teachers on their daily classroom teaching	10	100%
Pupils negative attitudes to work and examination fraud/malpractices	10	100%
Teachers poor attitude to work due to lack of incentives and other benefits	10	100%
Proprietors poor relationships with teachers	10	100%
Lack of teaching/learning materials e.g no science laboratories	10	100%

A giant stride is yet to be made by all stakeholders in education in order to meet the minimum goal of education for all (EFA) as propounded by the most recent decree of government education policy.

Among the numerous constraints, the most acute areas indicated by all (100%) ministry officials spelt out in table 7 include:

Understaffing particularly in specialized subject areas

Not enough time to discuss with teachers their daily classroom teaching

Pupils negative attitude to work and examination fraud/practices

Teacher's poor attitude to work due to lack of incentive and other benefits

Proprietor's poor relationship with teachers and lack of adequate teaching/learning materials such as science laboratory etc.

TABLE 8: number and percentage distribution of respondents (SMC Members) responsibilities/roles in private schools administration

ROLE/RESPONSIBILITIES	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
Monitoring and evaluating the daily activities of staff and pupils of the school	10	50
Approving the use of school finances in the interest of development	5	25
Recommend the recruitment and promotion of teachers to proprietors and government based on the prescribed code of conduct	3	15
Participate in the making of rules and regulations for staff and pupils of the school	2	10
TOTAL	20	100

TABLE 8 reveals that 50% of the school management committee members expressed their roles as the monitoring and evaluation of the daily activities of staff and pupils of the school. 25% mentioned approving the use of finances in the

interest of development, 15% recommending the recruitment and promotion of teachers to proprietors and government based on the prescribed code of conduct and 10% participate in the making of rules and regulations of staff and pupils of the school.

TABLE 9: number and percentage distribution of respondents (SMC Members) constraints in the dispensation of roles/duties

CONSTRAINTS/PROBLEMS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
Power from above	6	30
SMC discussions not implemented most times	5	25
Disagreement among members during crucial matters	2	10
Divergence in opinions due to personal affiliation	3	15
Submission to school heads due to illiteracy	4	20
TOTAL	20	100

Table 9 discusses the constraints of School Management Committee (SMC) members in carrying out their roles/duties. Its revealed 30% mentioned power from above as impediment to discussion making, 25% expressed that SMC discussions are mostly not implemented, 10% disagreement among members on crucial matters, 15% divergence of opinions due to personal affiliation and 20% expressed submission to school heads due to illiteracy of members.

TABLE 10: Number and Percentage Distribution of Respondents (Head Teachers) Administrative Roles in Private Schools

ADMINISTRATIVE ROLES	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
Making rules and regulations for staff and pupils	10	100
Holding of SMC meetings	10	100
Holding of CTA meetings	10	100
Attending meetings called by officials of the Ministry of Education Youth and Sport	10	100
Monitoring and reporting school matters to proprietor and other authorities	10	100

Table 10 highlights the administrative roles of head teachers in private schools. As indicated, all (100%) respondents expressed the following roles/responsibilities: making rules and regulations for staff and pupils, holding SMC and CTA meetings, attending meetings called by officials of Ministry of Education, monitoring and reporting school matters to proprietors and other higher authorities.

TABLE 11: number and percentage distribution of respondents (head teachers) mode of meetings held with CTA/SMC

FREQUENCY OF MEETINGS	SMC		CTA	
	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
Once per year	1	20	1	20
Twice per year	1	20	2	40
Three times per year	3	60	2	40
Others	-	-	-	-
Total	5	100	5	100

Table 11 explains that 20% of head teachers hold SMC meetings once and twice a year respectively, while 60% indicated three times per year. As for CTA meetings, 20% expressed once a year and 40% indicated twice and three times a year respectively.

It could be gathered from the table that there is need to improve on the number of meetings to be held during the year at both SMC and CTA levels.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that private schools came in to existence as a result of legislation mandate from the Government of Sierra Leone and that their function involves planning, organizing, directing, supervising, budgeting, delegation, monitoring and high evaluation of activities- thus making them distinct from government assisted school.

The study also established the fact that several individuals and groups have significant roles to play in the administration of private schools. Such individuals and groups include proprietor/proprietress, head teachers, the School Management Committees, PTA/CTA and officials of the Ministry of Education. Without cooperation among these major players in the administration of private primary schools, it will be difficult if not impossible for private schools to function well. Getting a good private school depends on apportioning tasks to these key stakeholders in the administration of private primary schools and making sure that such tasks are performed in the most efficient manner.

This study had proven that proprietors play several key roles in the administration of private schools. However, the research focused on presenting functions that cut across from all five selected private primary schools investigated.

According to the findings of this study, proprietors pay regular visits to their schools in a bid to supervise work of teachers for good practices which they may advice to be reinforced.

This study has proven that proprietors of private primary schools more or less act like entrepreneur in any business establishment. They provide one of the basic components of administration funds. With funds, other components of administration like personnel and place are provided to deliver the service of teaching and learning.

Proprietors of private schools design the school rules and regulations either single handedly or in collaboration with the SMC and head teacher. School rules here include rules governing the head teacher, teachers and pupils. In private schools where they have no SMC, like Jonathan's Child Care Private School, the proprietor makes rules and regulations governing the school.

In many private schools, the proprietor recruits the head teachers and the teaching staff. He/she may do this together with the SMC which in many cases he/she is part of. The proprietor can also dismiss a teacher and in some schools her dismissals are subject to the approval of the SMC which he/she is part of.

The proprietor/proprietress provides the money needed to run the school. For instance, teachers' salaries; providing

learning materials such as furniture, books, chalk and pay for the school building, water rate and electricity.

The proprietor/proprietress is the signatory to the school's account. Therefore he/she has the sole right to withdraw money from the school's account. It is only ZENITH INTERNATIONAL ACADEMY (ZIA) (one of the schools investigated) that a proprietor, with the Head teacher and Bursar are signatories to the school's account.

The School Management Committee in most private primary schools is appointed by the proprietor or proprietress and in most cases they are part of such committees.

In a school where the proprietor/proprietress is not part of SMC, the decision of the SMC is always subject to the approval of the proprietor.

The proprietor sets up conditions of service for the Head teacher and staffs. He/she may do this alone or with the advice of the School management committee (SMC)

Another key stakeholder in the administration of private primary schools is the head teacher. He plays the role of an administrator and supervisor, apart from defining and apportioning tasks to teachers, he/she sees to it that such tasks are carried out appropriately, the head teacher also acts as a bridge between the school and the proprietor, the school and the School Management Committee, the school and the parents, the school and the Ministry of Education.

Head teachers in private schools maintain grounds and buildings as well as property of the school. They see that the buildings are kept in good condition and that problems are reported promptly to the proprietor/proprietress for repairs.

Head teachers in private schools attend meetings called by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. They try to carry out the policy of the Ministry of Education in their schools.

The head teacher keeps the proprietor abreast with what is happening in the school. In such meetings with the proprietor and the SMC, he/she makes recommendations for the improvement of the school.

It is the responsibility of the head teacher to prepare the school records and make sure they are properly kept. Such records include: Syllabus, Admission Register, Scheme of work, record of work, Time book, Register, Lesson notes, sick report books etc.

Data collected for this study showed that head teachers in private primary schools are responsible for admission of pupils into the school. However, the setting up of conditions for admissions is not their sole prerogative.

Certificates, testimonials and report cards are signed by head teachers in private primary schools.

He/she plans and organizes the activities of the school.

The head teacher sees that his school reaches a high disciplinary and academic standard. He disciplines both pupils and teachers appropriately.

He/she calls staff meetings to discuss pertinent issues that affect the school. In such meetings, he/she, together with the teaching staff identify problems and come up with ways of amending such problems.

The head teachers in most private primary schools prepare the school's budget for every academic year. This budget is subject to the approval of the proprietor or board.

The School Management Committee more or less acts as an advisory council and one brain behind what operates in private primary schools. They brainstorm and suggest positive things that may bring development and raise the standard of the schools.

The School management Committee (SMC) in private primary schools makes rules and regulations. In some of the schools investigated, the proprietor and or Head teacher is part of the board.

The School Management Committee serves as a check on the authority of the head teacher. That is, some of the decisions taken by the head teacher are subject to the approval of the SMC.

The SMC serves as advisory council to the proprietor; they make selfless contributions to the proprietor for the improvement of the school.

The SMC listens to complaints and suggestions from teachers and head teachers and acts upon them accordingly.

In most private schools, the SMC serves as the panel for the recruitment of teachers.

For the Ministry of Education, the inspectorate helps the government to run all educational policies smoothly. Their frequent visits to private primary schools is to make sure that the educational policy set up by government is implemented to the letter.

The Ministry of Education sends inspectors to private schools to oversee their activities and make sure that government's policies are implemented correctly in the school. Among the functions of inspectors of school are:

Inspectors pay regular visits to private primary schools and arrange full scale school supervision.

Inspectors during their visits to private primary schools inspect the following: physical facilities, recreational facilities, toilet facilities, and water facilities, the curriculum, relevant school records, time table, registers, sitting accommodation, note of lessons, financial records etc.

Inspectors also ask for the Ministry's official letter of approval.

If the school has some requirement deficiency, inspectors from the Ministry, render advice to the administration, and interpret the policy for correct implementation.

If a teacher is found not having the required qualifications or not doing his/her work well, inspector's advice the teacher in question. They may query authorities concerned and if no change occurs, they ask the school to terminate the services of such teachers.

The parents pay fees for their children/wards that form the nucleus of the funding that is needed to run the administration of the school.

Parents complement the effort of private schools by studying or making arrangements for studying their kids and also play a great role in proper socialization of their children.

Parents provide motivation for their children especially when they succeed. This helps to enhance learning and makes work lighter for teachers and other school administrators.

According to the findings of this study, private primary schools face financial problems. For instance, lack of funds for expansion and development, the administration also needs funds for maintenance of school building and furniture. Adequate and appropriate teaching and learning materials are not provided because of lack of funds.

Teachers always agitate for better conditions of service and better pay. When this is not provided the teacher is not motivated to teach the children well and standard will fall which results to pressure on the administration.

If Parents do not pay fees on time, this will hinder the work of the administrator. This is so because school fees for most private schools are the life blood that keeps the school going. Some parents do not complement the effort of the school and some even contradict the school or teachers.

Private schools are not one hundred percent receiving assistance from the Ministry of Education. This is frustrating to the administration and they have to charge exorbitant fees for the school to survive.

Teachers who leave the school before the end of the academic year create the problem of looking for replacement at an odd time of the academic year.

Suggestions and Recommendations

The proprietors of private schools should improve the conditions of service in their schools so as to retain or attract excellent teachers.

The head teacher with the support of the proprietor and School Management Committee should make provision for the improvement of their staff – example, study leave and organizing special programs (courses) for the improvement of their teaching staff.

The government should not close the doors on their privileges to teachers of private schools. Teachers in this school should be given the opportunity to benefit from government grants in aids (SLG) like teachers from government schools or government assisted schools.

Government should design and enforce policy restricting teachers leaving the classroom before the end of the academic year.

Parents must pay school fees on time to help cushion the financial problems faced by most private schools.

Government must put a regulatory mechanism in place and enforce it particularly on high school fees and other charges levied by private schools if their objectives on Education for all (EFA) are to be achieved.

Ministry of Education must ensure that all private primary schools within the Bo City have standing management committees.

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